

Interest Rate Liberalisation and Investment in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of interest rate liberalization on investment in Nigeria from 1986-2023 using data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin. The data were subjected to various diagnostic tests such as Unit Root, ARCH, Normality, among others, and the result revealed that the data were suitable for estimation. The dependent variable was represented by Gross Fixed Capital Formation used as a proxy for investment, while Exchange Rate, Government Expenditure, Interest Rate, Inflation and Money Supply were the independent variables. The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation technique was employed to test the short and long run impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The ARDL long and short run results revealed that Government Expenditure and Interest Rate significantly impacted on investment during the period under review showcasing the importance of these variables in promoting investment in Nigeria. The result further revealed the need to. strengthen policies that would promote stable exchange and inflation rate that would enhance domestic investment. Based on the findings of this study, it is pertinent to maintain macroeconomic stability through sound monetary and fiscal policies as well as strategic investments in infrastructure, education, and regulatory reforms, for a more robust and diversified economy.

Keywords: Investment, Interest Rate Liberalisation, and Auto Regressive Distributed Lag.

1.1 Introduction

Over the past years, interest rate liberalisation has played a significant role in Nigeria's economic policy changes. In an effort to promote a more market-oriented financial sector and deregulate interest rates, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has put in place a number of initiatives. These actions have included the introduction of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) and the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) as the main instruments for monetary policy, as well as the Treasury Single Account (TSA), (CBN, 2022). Nigeria's liberalisation of interest rates has a complex justification. Since market-determined interest rates are intended to represent the real potential cost of capital, proponents contend that loosening interest rate regulations can boost the efficiency with which financial resources are allocated. It is thought that resources will flow to their most productive uses if interest rates are allowed to freely fluctuate in response to market conditions, which will encourage investment and economic progress. The possible effects of interest rate liberalization on income distribution, small and medium-sized businesses

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(SMEs), and financial stability are frequently brought up by opponents of the policy (Anyanwu, 2014). Furthermore, variables such as the macroeconomic environment, the depth and efficiency of the financial markets, financial institutions and regulatory frameworks may have an impact on how well interest rate liberalisation stimulates investment in Nigeria (Ezejiolor, 2018).

Interest rate liberalisation has been a frequently adopted policy instrument worldwide, especially in developing nations such as Nigeria, with the objective of promoting the growth of the financial sector and encouraging investment. Due to its importance for economic growth and development, policy makers have paid close attention to the link between interest rate liberalisation and investment in recent years. Theoretically, interest rate liberalisation should encourage investment by lowering capital costs and expanding credit availability, but empirical research from recent studies has produced contradictory results.

According to empirical studies, interest rate liberalisation and investment in Nigeria are positively correlated. Ajide, Lawanson, and Ogundipe (2020), for instance, discovered that interest rate liberalisation encouraged private investment in Nigeria, which raised capital creation and spurred economic expansion. Ajide, Lawanson, and Ogundipe (2020), contend that interest rate liberalisation encourages financial institution rivalry, which lowers lending rates and improves investor access to credit. Other research, however, has drawn attention to the difficulties and ambiguities surrounding the effect of interest rate liberalisation on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. According to Umar and Opeyemi (2021), interest rate liberalisation lessens the monetary policy's ability to influence investment choices by complicating the process by which it is transmitted. Umar and Opeyemi (2021), contend that interest rate swings, which are impacted by a number of internal and external variables, make investors uneasy and have a detrimental impact on their choice of investments.

The study of Onifade and Alamu (2022), drew attention to the possible dangers of interest rate liberalisation in the absence of sufficient regulatory frameworks and macroeconomic stability measures. These risks include; the possibility for increase in interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate volatility, all of which might discourage investment. Given these conflicting results, it is pertinent that more empirical investigation is required to fully comprehend the relationship between interest rate liberalisation and investment in Nigeria.

Policymakers may improve the efficacy of interest rate liberalisation policies and encourage sustained investment development in Nigeria by looking at the fundamental causes of the inconsistent results seen in empirical research. In many emerging economies, including Nigeria, interest rate liberalisation has been a crucial policy change intended to promote the growth of the financial sector and encourage investment. While interest rate liberalisation theoretically encourages competition among financial institutions, resulting in lower lending rates, Ajide, Lawanson, and Ogundipe (2020) contended that in actuality, the transmission mechanism is frequently inefficient, suggesting that investors' borrowing costs remain high. Additionally, data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) shows that lending rates are still high, which limits investment activity, even after interest rate liberalisation measures have been implemented (CBN, 2022).

Also, there are major barriers to interest rate liberalization's ability to effectively encourage investment due to the makeup of the Nigerian financial system. According to Ogunmuyiwa and Aluko (2020), investment is hampered by the dominance of risk-free

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government securities and the weakness of the capital market, which prevents the positive effect of a lower interest rate from reaching the real sector of the economy. Thus, this study aims to offer a thorough examination of the relationship between interest rate liberalisation and investment in Nigeria as well as the causal link between interest rate liberalisation and investment in Nigeria. The study analyses data spanning from 1986 to 2023.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Interest Rate

Irving Fisher (1930), defined interest rate as the price paid for the use of money over time, represented as a percentage of the principal amount borrowed or lent. According to Fisher's definition, interest rates are a measure of the cost of borrowing or the return on investment related to using money. A percentage of the transaction's principle is used to express this cost or return. Fisher's concept also emphasizes the time value of money, implying that variables like risk, opportunity cost, and inflation affect how much money is worth over time. Interest rates therefore function as a tool to reimburse borrowers for the expense of obtaining funds and to compensate lenders for delaying investment or consumption. All things considered, Fisher's concept emphasizes the basic function of interest rates in enabling resource allocation, impacting investment choices, and determining an economy's overall performance.

Keynes defined interest rates as the reward for parting with liquidity, with higher rates compensating for the risk of holding fewer liquid assets, as outlined in "The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money" (Keynes, 1936). In "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money," John Maynard Keynes states that interest rates can be defined in relation to the liquidity preference theory. The term "liquidity preference," coined by Keynes, describes people's preference for holding liquid assets like cash as opposed to illiquid ones like bonds or securities.

According to Keynes' (1936), the relationship between the money supply and demand in the economy sets the interest rate. Interest rates are especially driven by people's demand for liquidity, which is impacted by a range of variables including opportunity cost of holding money, projections about the future, and uncertainty. People who have a strong desire for liquidity may tolerate lower interest rates in exchange for the option to hold onto their money rather than invest in volatile assets. On the other hand, when consumers have a low preference for liquidity, they are more likely to accept poorer returns on their investments in exchange for parting with their money, that is, to demand higher interest rates. Overall, Keynes' definition suggests that psychological and behavioural elements that affect people's demand for liquidity also have an impact on interest rates, in addition to the cost of borrowing and return on investment.

Obi (2015) defines interest rate as the cost of borrowing money from financial institutions or the payment made for lending money to borrowers in the context of the financial market in his study on interest rate dynamics and economic growth in Nigeria. Obi's definition indicates that interest rates regulate economic funding. Higher interest rates increase the cost of borrowing, which may discourage borrowing and investment and limit economic growth. However, lower interest rates cut borrowing costs, which may boost investment and ultimately affect economic growth.

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2.1.2 Investment

Keynes (1936) defines investment as the expenditure on new capital goods that are expected to provide returns over time. This concept says that investment involves allocating resources towards the production or acquisition of assets with the anticipation of earning future income or profits. Keynes' concept argues that investment is crucial for generating aggregate demand and driving economic expansion. When businesses invest in new capital goods, they stimulate demand for goods and services, ultimately enhancing economic activity. Additionally, investment leads to the expansion of productive capacity, innovation, and technical improvement, which are vital for long-term economic development.

The cornerstone of Keynes' theory of investment is the concept of the Marginal Efficiency of Capital (MEC). The marginal efficiency of capital refers to the projected rate of return on an additional unit of capital invested. In other words, it refers to the increased profit margin or effectiveness that arises from the purchase of one more capital good. According to Keynes, businesses evaluate potential investments by contrasting the current interest rate with the predicted return on a project. An investment is considered financially viable if its marginal earnings curve (MEC) exceeds the interest rate, indicating the possibility of generating returns higher than the financing costs. On the other hand, if the MEC is less than the interest rate, businesses can decide to put off or abandon investment projects since the returns wouldn't be high enough to cover the financing costs.

Many variables, including market conditions, technology developments, profitability projections for the future, and uncertainty levels, all have an impact on the marginal efficiency of capital. Keynes proposed that changes in the MEC might cause changes in investment spending, which would then cause changes in aggregate demand and economic instability.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

2.2.1 The Classical Theory of Interest Rates

Economists like Adam Smith (1776), David Ricardo (1817), and John Stuart Mill (1848), promoted the classical theory of interest rates, which provides an essential understanding of how interest rates are set in financial markets. The classical viewpoint shows that interest rates indicate the expense of borrowing money as well as the reward for saving. A portion of an individual's income is saved by them and deposited in financial institutions, where it is lent to borrowers for investment reasons. Interest rates, which represent the opportunity cost of using resources now rather than putting money aside for future use, encourage people to save. According to the traditional view, interest rates change to balance saving and investing. When saving outpaces investment, the financial market has an excess supply of money, pushing interest rates lower. On the other hand, when investment outpaces saving, there is an excess demand for money, which drives up interest rates. Interest rates adjust until it reaches a point where saving and investing are equal, or market equilibrium.

2.2.2 The Loanable Funds Theory of Interest Rate

The loanable funds or Neo-Classical Theory of interest rates, pioneered by economists like Irving Fisher (1930), provides valuable insights into how interest rates are determined in financial markets. This theory extends the classical economic framework and underscores the significance of saving and investment in shaping interest

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rate dynamics. According to the loanable funds theory, interest rates adjust to equate the supply of savings (loanable funds) with the demand for investment. Individuals and institutions supply funds to financial markets by saving a portion of their income, while borrowers demand funds for investment purposes. Interest rates are the price that balances supply and demand for loanable funds.

The loanable funds theory implies that changes in factors such as time preference, productivity of capital, and government borrowing can influence the supply and demand for loanable funds, thereby affecting interest rate dynamics in the economy. For example, an increase in savings rates may lead to a higher supply of loanable funds, a decrease in interest rates, stimulating investment and economic activity.

Furthermore, the loanable funds theory underscores the importance of financial intermediaries, such as banks and other financial institutions, in facilitating the transfer of funds between savers and borrowers. These intermediaries play a crucial role in channeling savings into productive investments, thereby contributing to economic growth and development.

2.2.3 Keynes Liquidity Preference Theory of Interest Rate

The Keynesian Liquidity Preference Theory of Interest Rate, proposed by John Maynard Keynes (1936), presents a departure from the traditional views of interest rate determination. Rather than focusing solely on the supply and demand for loanable funds, Keynes emphasizes the role of individuals' preference for liquidity, or the desire to hold money rather than other assets. Keynes identifies three main motives for holding money: the transactions motive, precautionary motive, and speculative motive. The transactions motive refers to the need to hold money for everyday transactions, such as buying goods and services. The precautionary motive arises from the desire to hold money as a buffer against unforeseen expenses or emergencies. Finally, the speculative motive involves holding money in anticipation of changes in asset prices, with the aim of profiting from future market movements.

According to the Liquidity Preference Theory, interest rates adjust to balance the demand for money, driven by these motives, with the supply of money in the economy. When individuals have a strong preference for liquidity, they are reluctant to part with their money, leading to a decrease in the supply of loanable funds available for lending. As a result, interest rates rise to entice lenders to part with their money. Thus, when liquidity preference is low, individuals are more willing to invest their money, increasing the supply of loanable funds and driving interest rates down.

2.3 Theories of Investment

2.3.1 The Accelerator Theory of Investment

In Dale's (1967) exposition of the accelerator theory of investment, the central idea revolves around the relationship between changes in the level of aggregate demand and fluctuations in investment expenditure. The accelerator theory posits that changes in the rate of growth of aggregate demand, particularly in consumer demand, directly influence the level of investment spending by firms. According to this theory, variations in consumer demand, which are generally driven by changes in income levels, translate into swings in the demand for goods and services. Firms respond to these fluctuations in demand by altering their investment expenditures in line with the projected level of demand for their products. Specifically, when there is a surge in consumer demand, firms anticipate bigger sales volumes and, subsequently, increase their investment in capital

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goods to expand production capacity and fulfill the increased demand. Conversely, if consumer demand weakens or falls, enterprises may scale back their investment spending to avoid excess capacity or inventory building. This dynamic link between changes in aggregate demand and investment expenditure provides the basis of the accelerator theory.

2.3.2 The Classical Theory of Investment

According to Jhingan (2010), the classical theory of investment places significant emphasis on the pivotal role of savings, capital accumulation, and productivity in shaping investment decisions and fostering economic growth. The theory emphasizes that savings constitute a portion of income set aside for future utilization rather than immediate consumption. These saved funds are subsequently directed towards various investment avenues, including the acquisition of capital goods and the financing of infrastructure projects. Such investments contribute to the overall accumulation of capital within the economy. Furthermore, the theory underscores the critical importance of enhancing productivity through investments in technology, innovation, and education. These efforts are aimed at enhancing efficiency and competitiveness, thereby resulting in heightened output and long-term economic prosperity.

2.3.4 The Neo-Classical Theory of Investment

Jorgenson (1967) presents a neoclassical theory of investment that extends classical economic principles to elucidate investment decisions in contemporary economies. This theory emphasizes the pivotal role of expected rates of return and the cost of capital in driving business behavior. According to this theory, firms make investment decisions based on their assessment of the potential profitability of investment projects, comparing the anticipated returns from additional capital investment with the associated costs, including interest rates, technological advancements, and prevailing market conditions. Central to the Neo-Classical framework is the idea of the marginal productivity of capital, which denotes the incremental output produced by each unit of capital investment. Firms allocate resources to various investment efforts based on marginal productivity, prioritizing projects with higher expected returns. Additionally, the theory underscores the significance of the cost of capital, encompassing both borrowing prices and the opportunity cost of utilizing funds for investment rather than alternative uses. Fluctuations in the cost of capital exert an impact on firms' investment decisions, with lower costs stimulating greater investment activity and higher costs dampening investment enthusiasm.

Keynes (1936), on the other hand, posits that investment decisions are primarily driven by expectations and uncertainty rather than objective assessments of expected returns and costs. Investment performed by private sector enterprises is determined by the interest rate. Accordingly, investment decisions are made by comparing the marginal efficiency of capital (MEC) or yield with the real rate of interest. As long as the MEC is greater than the interest rate, new investment in plants, equipment, and machinery will take place. However, when more and more capital is used in the production process, the MEC will reduce due to the diminishing marginal product of capital.

2.4 Empirical Literature

Mackinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) conducted a groundbreaking study that paved the way for a significant amount of empirical research into the functioning of financially suppressed economies and the positive impacts of financial liberalization. The primary contention in the research was that a financial system that is repressed is detrimental to growth and development because of the negative consequences that it has on the mobilization of savings and the distribution of capital. The liberalization of the financial sector, on the other hand, will result in an increase in savings, will boost investment, and will cause economic growth. In a number of empirical research, it has been demonstrated that higher real interest rates can increase the amount of money invested. The supply of domestic funding to finance investment is increased by higher rates. According to the McKinnon and Shaw doctrine, financial repression occurs primarily when a country imposes low-level ceilings on nominal deposits and lending interest rates relative to inflation, resulting in low or negative real interest rates that discourage savings mobilization and the channeling of mobilized savings through the financial system.

The study by Effiong (2020) has explored how interest rate affects the real sector output growth in Nigeria. With data from 1985 to 2019 which was analyzed using error correction model, there was a long run relationship between interest rate and economic growth. The estimate showed that interest rate exerted a negative and significant effect on real sector output in Nigeria. The study recommended that monetary policy should be geared towards keeping interest rate at a favourable level.

Also, Effiong, Ukere and Ekpe (2024) examined how fiscal policy and interest rate affects the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy. The study utilized the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique on data from 1981 to 2021. It was observed that while government spending negatively affected manufacturing sector's performance in the short run, value added tax had a positive effect. However, the short run effect of interest rate was positive and significant. The study recommended that government spending should be channelled to productive sectors of the economy; and that interest rates should be managed effectively to enhance productivity in the manufacturing sector.

Inyang (2018) conducted a study that looked at the effects of interest rate liberalization in Nigeria over a 31-year period, from 1986 to 2016. The study looked at the short-term relationships between the study's variables, investment, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates. The impact of interest rates on investment in Nigeria was investigated using ordinary least square regression, and the causal relationship between interest rates and investment in Nigeria was ascertained through the pairwise Granger causality test. The findings indicated that interest rates had a negative and negligible effect on investment in Nigeria. The study suggested that interest rates be set so as not to discourage investors from taking out loans in order to start profitable investment projects.

Davis and Emerenini (2015) conducted a study to analyse the influence of interest rates on investment in Nigeria during the period from 1986 to 2012. The study used multiple regressions as a statistical method, demonstrating that high interest rates have a detrimental impact on investment. Based on the results, the study proposed several recommendations. These include the need for the appropriate monetary authority to

develop policies that promote savings and decrease the prime lending rate for legitimate investors, among other suggestions.

Udonsah (2012) conducted a study on the effect of interest rates on investment decisions made in Nigeria. An econometric study was conducted for the time span from 1981 to 2010. Secondary data was gathered from the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) statistical bulletin (volume 21) in December 2010. Data was collected, and an empirical analysis was done. Multiple regression was used in assessing the data on the influence of the interest rate on Nigeria prior to interest rate regulation in 1986 and served as guidance on how the interest rate can be fixed to enhance the effective accumulation of savings that can be directed to investment. According to the research, CBN should be autonomous and not under government control. The CBN has the ability to establish an open market operation for government borrowing. This would not only limit government expenditure to its revenue, but it would also help stabilize the investment rate according to the principles of the free market. As a result, the traditional link between the interest rate and public investment will be reestablished.

Onwumere, Okore and Imo (2012) were of the view that interest rate liberalization causes interest rates to rise, thereby increasing savings and investment. The research covered the period of 1976 to 1999 and adopted the OLS technique using SPSS statistical software. The study reveals that interest rate liberalization has a negative significant impact on investment in Nigeria; only real lending rate was used in estimation of investment. Thus, interest rate liberalization, though a good policy was counterproductive in Nigeria. This might be as a result of improper pace and sequencing.

Eregha (2010) examined variations in interest rate and investment determination in Nigeria between the periods of 1970 to 2002, using instrumental variable technique. The study showed that investment has an indirect relationship with interest rate variation and other variables that was employed. These variables such as debt burden, economic stability, foreign exchange, shortage and lack of infrastructure affect gross investment, and the OLS technique was employed.

Akintoye & Olowlaju (2008) examined optimum macroeconomic investment decision in Nigeria. The study employed OLS and VAR frameworks to simulate and inter-temporarily private investment response to its principal shock namely public investment, domestic credit and output shock. The study found low interest rates have constrained investment growth. The study resolved that only government policies produce sustainable output, steady public investment and encourage domestic credit to the private sector will promote private investment.

Akiri & Adofu (2007), investigated the effect of interest rate deregulation on investment in Nigeria between 1986-2002 and uses OLS regression model to authenticate the proficiency of interest rate deregulation on gross domestic investment in Nigeria. The study also identified other factors which impede investment in Nigeria namely, political instability, exchange rate, inflation rate, unawareness of investment opportunities and corruption in order to bring out the level of influence of exchange rate and inflation on investment.

Chuba (2005), investigated the validity of the proposition that the high internet rate observed during the era of post liberalization on interest rate have been frequently

blamed for the investment contraction in Nigeria. The study makes use of descriptive and analytical tools; the findings shows that real lending rate have a negative but insignificant impact on gross domestic investment (GDI) and that interest rate liberalization does not negative impact GDI as usually claimed.

The findings of Givoannini (1983, 1985), Corbo& Schmidt-Hebbel (1992), Schmidt-Hebbel, Webb &Corsetti (1992) and Edwards (1994) found that savings is insensitive to real interest rate and are in direct contradiction to real life experiences and empirical evidence in Nigeria. Soyibo and Adekanye (1992), in their investigation of the relationship between aggregate and interest rate in Nigeria used OLS regression model but in a log form and found aggregate savings to be positively correlated with real interest rates.

2.5 Justification of the study

Despite the extensive research on Interest rate liberalization and investment in Nigeria, there still remains a notable gap regarding the role of public expenditure in this context. Existing studies have predominantly focused on variables such as interest rates, investment, inflation, exchange rates, and savings rates. However, the impact of public expenditure, particularly its interaction with financial liberalization policies, has not been thoroughly investigated.

To this end, this research incorporates public expenditure variables into the analysis of interest rate liberalization and investment in Nigeria. Public expenditure can significantly influence economic activity, affecting both the supply and demand sides of the economy. By including variables such as government spending on infrastructure, education, healthcare, and other public services, the research aims to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how financial liberalization interacts with public sector activity to influence investment in Nigeria. Also, this study uses the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation technique to investigate the long and short run relationship between interest rate liberalization and investment in Nigeria.

3.1 Research Methodology

3.1.1 Model Specification

The model in a functional form is stated thus;

$$GFCF = F(INRLEND, EXR, LNPUBEXP, INF, MS).....(1)$$

Where:

GFCF	=	Growth rate of Gross Fixed Capital Formation (a proxy for Investment)
EXR	=	Exchange rate
INRLEND	=	Interest rate
LNPUBEXP	=	Public expenditure as a percentage of GDP
INF	=	Inflation
MS	=	Money Supply as a percentage of GDP

Transforming equation (1) to a linear econometric model gives;

$$GFCF = \beta_0 + \beta_1INRLEND + \beta_2EXR + \beta_3LNPUBEXP + \beta_4INF + \beta_5MS+ \mu.....(2)$$

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A priori, $\beta_0 > 0$; $\beta_1 < 0$; $\beta_2 < 0$; $\beta_3 > 0$; $\beta_4 < 0$; $\beta_5 > 0$

3.1.2 Technique Employed

The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag model is employed in this study due to its ability to capture the short-term and long-term relationships of the dependent and the independent variables. This makes it the ideal method to achieve the objective of the research work, ensuring accurate and meaningful results. The study also uses the Granger Causality Test in order to determine the causal relationship among the variables employed in the study.

The Unit root test and the F-Bound testis are used to test for the stationarity and cointegration of the variables respectively.

3.2 Description of variables

i. Gross Capital Formation:

This is the total value of a country's new investments in fixed assets, such as buildings, machinery, and equipment, excluding land purchases. It represents the net increase in physical assets within an economy and includes expenditures on both replacement and new additions to these fixed assets.

ii. Interest Rate

Interest rate refers to the cost of borrowing or the return generated on savings or investments, expressed as a percentage of the principal amount. It reflects the compensation provided by borrowers to lenders for the use of their fund, or the benefit obtained by savers or investors for postponing consumption or taking on risk. Interest rates have a vital role in determining borrowing and lending decisions, investment choices, and general economic activity

iii. Exchange Rate:

This is the rate at which one country's currency is exchanged for another. For the purpose of this study, the exchange rate used is the naira/dollar exchange rates in the formal market.

iv. Public Expenditure:

This refers to the spending made by the government or public sector institutions on goods, services, and obligations. Public expenditure can either be capital or recurrent. For the purpose of this study, an aggregate of both capital and recurrent expenditure is used.

v. Inflation Rate:

Inflation is a sustained increase in the price level of goods and services in an economy over a period of time. The inflation rate is the annual percentage change in a general price index, usually the consumer price index over time.

vi. Money Supply(M₂):

Money supply refers to the total amount of money available in an economy at a particular point in time. It includes various forms of money, such as cash, coins, and balances held in checking and savings accounts.

4.1 Data Presentation and Discussion of Result

4.1.1 Stylized Facts

Figure 4.1: Trend Analysis of Gross Fixed Capital Formation and Exchange Rate.

The graph of Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) typically represents investment levels for the years under review. The trend shows a decline from 2010 onwards as possibly due to global financial instabilities and internal economic challenges. The sharp drops around 2016 coincide with Nigeria's economic recession, exacerbated by falling oil prices and foreign investment withdrawals. Figure 4.1 also shows that Exchange Rate (EXR) has been significantly volatile, especially during major economic downturns. From its stability in 1987, it soared to over N425/dollar in 2022, reflecting persistent inflationary pressures on the Nigerian economy.

Figure 4.2: Trend Analysis of Public Expenditure, Interest Rate and Inflation

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Figure 4.2 shows that Public Expenditure indicates a gradual increase, reflecting government efforts to stimulate the economy through public spending. However, this also indicates a growing dependency on government spending to drive economic activities, which can lead to unsustainable fiscal deficits if not properly managed. Interest Rates (INR.LEND) as seen in the Figure 4.2, initially decreased, which should theoretically encourage borrowing and investment. However, the high rates from the 2000s onward, combined with economic uncertainty, could stifle private investment. Inflation (INF) has been erratic, with periods of extreme inflation noted in the late 1980s and mid-2010s. High inflation erodes real earnings and savings, reducing the disposable income available for investment.

4.2 Analysis and Interpretation of Result

4.2.1 Unit Root Test Result

Table 4.1 Result of Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF t-statistics	Probability value	Level of integration
GFCF	-5.672281	0.0000	I(1)
EXR	-3.628575	0.0100	I(1)
LNPubExp	-3.108582	0.0359	I(0)
INR.LEND	-4.327772	0.0078	I(0)
INF	-3.533848	0.0012	I(0)
MS	-4.949762	0.0003	I(1)

Source: Computed by the Researcher from E-VIEWS 10

The unit root test results as shown in Table 4.1 provide a critical examination of the stationarity of the variables included in the model. The result showed that the variables are stationary at levels and first difference., suggesting potential use of techniques such as the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) to capture both short-term dynamics and long-term relationships of the variables.

4.2.2 The F - Bound Test Result

Table 4.2 The F-Bounds Test Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	3.246046	10%	2.08	3
K	5	5%	2.39	3.38
		2.5%	2.7	3.73
		1%	3.06	4.15

Source: Computed by the Researcher using E-VIEWS 10

The F-bounds test is a key component of the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) approach, used to determine whether there is a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables in the model. The result suggests that there is existence of cointegration relationship

4.2.3 The ARDL Long Run Result

Table 4.3 Long run Estimate (ADRL)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t-Statistics	Prob.
EXR	0.005933	0.022777	0.260477	0.7983
LNPubExp	4.427038	2.165816	2.044051	0.0402
INR.LEND	0.580099	0.210826	2.751555	0.0156
INF	-0.065268	0.064277	-1.015412	0.3271
MS	-0.252055	0.203405	-1.239174	0.2357
C	5.929588	24.55195	0.241512	0.8127

Source: Computed by the Researcher from E-VIEWS 10

4.3 Long-Run ARDL Results

The long run result in Table 4.3 shows that government expenditure and interest rate showed significant impacts on investment measured by Gross Fixed Capital Formation. However, exchange rate, inflation and money supply displayed insignificant relationship with investment in the long run.

4.4 Short Run ARDL Result

Table 4.4: Short run Estimate (ARDL)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t-Statistics	Prob.
EXR	0.005933	0.012162	0.487842	0.6332
LNPubExp	4.427038	1.300695	3.403595	0.0043
INR.LEND	0.580099	0.125250	4.631545	0.0004
INF	-0.065268	0.032345	-2.017856	0.0632
MS	-0.696538	0.390498	-1.783718	0.0962
ECM (-1)	-0.361868	0.063515	-5.697408	0.0001

R-squared	0.871701	Mean dependent var	-0.966481
Adjusted R-squared	0.788307	S.D. dependent var	3.009759
S.E. of regression	1.384793	Akaike info criterion	3.781879
Sum squared resid	38.35302	Schwarz criterion	4.410381
Log likelihood	-50.29195	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.996216
Durbin-Watson stat	2.001871		

Source: Computed by the Researcher from E-VIEWS 10

The short-run ARDL results in Table 4.4 provide insights into the effects of changes in the independent variables on dependent variable in Nigeria. These results highlight the dynamic adjustments that occur before reaching the long-run equilibrium. The error correction model which measures the speed of adjustment from disequilibrium to equilibrium showed 0.36. This means that approximately 36% of the disequilibrium is corrected within a year. The result further indicates that government expenditure and interest rate were significant at 5% level in the short run, while inflation and money supply were significant at 10% during the same period. However, exchange rate showed an insignificant relationship with investment within the period under review.

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The result showed the explanatory power of the independent variables on the dependent variable to be 87%. This means that 87% variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable, while the remaining 13% is captured by the error term. The DW d-statistic showed the absence of autocorrelation in the model. The Diagnostic test result in Table 4.5 confirms that the variables used in this study are suitable for estimation and the model appears robust with no significant issues detected.

4.5 The Diagnostic Test Result

Table 4.5 Diagnostic Test

Test	F-statistics	Probability value
ARCH	0.3758	0.9786
LM TEST	2.3694	0.1357
NORMALITY TEST	1.8373	0.3991
RESET TEST	0.7240	0.4102

Source: Computed by the Researcher using E-VIEWS 10

4.6 The Granger Causality Test

TABLE 4.6 Granger Causality Test Results

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Sample: 1986 2023

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
EXR does not Granger Cause GFCF	36	0.87349	0.4275
GFCF does not Granger Cause EXR		1.22434	0.3078
INF does not Granger Cause GFCF	36	2.59008	0.0912
GFCF does not Granger Cause INF		6.85041	0.0034
INR_LEND does not Granger Cause GFCF	36	0.38804	0.6816
GFCF does not Granger Cause INRLEND		3.91282	0.0305
LNPUBEXP does not Granger Cause GFCF	36	3.62122	0.0386
GFCF does not Granger Cause LNPUBEXP		0.05224	0.9492
MS does not Granger Cause GFCF	36	0.57140	0.5706
GFCF does not Granger Cause MS		1.82032	0.1789
INF does not Granger Cause EXR	36	1.28295	0.2915
EXR does not Granger Cause INF		0.96032	0.3939
INR_LEND does not Granger Cause EXR	36	0.46255	0.6339
EXR does not Granger Cause INRLEND		4.78849	0.0154
LNPUBEXP does not Granger Cause EXR	36	1.99658	0.1529
EXR does not Granger Cause LNPUBEXP		0.17217	0.8426
MS does not Granger Cause EXR	36	0.78347	0.4657
EXR does not Granger Cause MS		1.19135	0.3173

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INR_LEND does not Granger Cause INF	36	1.42829	0.2551
INF does not Granger Cause INRLEND		3.05153	0.0617
LNPUBEXP does not Granger Cause INF	36	4.35708	0.0215
INF does not Granger Cause LNPUBEXP		0.72184	0.4938
MS does not Granger Cause INF	36	0.94606	0.3992
INF does not Granger Cause MS		3.29145	0.0506
LNPUBEXP does not Granger Cause INRLEND	36	6.46468	0.0045
INR_LEND does not Granger Cause LNPUBEXP		0.05019	0.9511
MS does not Granger Cause INR_LEND	36	2.29913	0.1172
INR_LEND does not Granger Cause MS		1.99887	0.1526
MS does not Granger Cause LNPUBEXP	36	0.31457	0.7324
LNPUBEXP does not Granger Cause MS		2.24864	0.1225

Source: Computed by the Researcher using E-VIEWS 10

Table 4.6 presents the causality analysis of the variables employed in the study. The result reveals that some variables displayed unidirectional causality, while others showed absence of causality relationship. The result reveals unidirectional causality on Gross Fixed Capital Formation and Inflation; Gross Fixed Capital Formation and Interest Rate; Government Expenditure and Gross Fixed Capital Formation; Exchange Rate and Interest Rate; Government Expenditure and Inflation; Inflation and Money Supply, and Government Expenditure and Interest Rate.

4.2 Discussion of Finding

The findings of this study reveal important insights into the impact of interest rate liberalization on investment in Nigeria,. The results suggest a complex relationship between variables like interest rates and investment, highlighting both the potentials and limitations of interest rate liberalization as a policy tool. In examining the long-term effects, the regression analysis indicates that interest rates (INR.LEND) and public expenditure (PubExp) significantly influence investment, suggesting that these factors are crucial for stimulating economic activity. This aligns with Keynesian theory, which posits that fiscal policy and financial market efficiency can drive investment and economic growth (Blanchard & Johnson, 2013). However, the lack of significant impact from exchange rates (EXR), inflation (INF), and money supply (MS) on investment challenges traditional economic assumptions and points to the unique characteristics of the Nigerian economy.

The short-run dynamics provide further clarity, revealing that public expenditure and interest rates have immediate and significant effects on investment. The significant error correction term indicates that deviations from the long-run equilibrium are quickly corrected, underscoring the stability of the investment model. This suggests that while interest rate liberalization can enhance financial efficiency, its effectiveness in promoting investment relies heavily on complementary fiscal policies (Broner and Ventura, 2010).

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This highlights the importance of a coordinated policy approach that addresses both monetary and fiscal dimensions to effectively stimulate investment. The high R-squared value of the model further supports this, indicating that the selected variables effectively capture the dynamics of investment. However, the findings also suggest that interest rate liberalization alone may not be sufficient to drive investment growth, necessitating a broader policy framework that includes fiscal measures and structural reforms.

The Granger causality tests provide valuable insights into the causal links between the variables, revealing that investment Granger-causes both inflation and interest rates. This finding suggests that investment decisions in Nigeria have broader macroeconomic implications, influencing key economic indicators over time. The causality from public expenditure to investment underscores the critical role of government spending in driving economic activity, aligning with the Keynesian view that fiscal policy is essential for stimulating growth.

Despite these findings, the absence of significant causality from interest rates to investment challenges the efficacy of interest rate liberalization as a standalone policy measure. This indicates that while liberalization efforts can improve financial market efficiency, there should be complemented by supportive fiscal policies and structural reforms to effectively stimulate investment. This highlights the importance of a comprehensive policy approach that addresses the underlying constraints facing the Nigerian economy, such as infrastructural deficits and limited access to finance.

It is crucial to recognize that the Nigerian economy faces structural challenges that limit the effectiveness of interest rate liberalization. For instance, infrastructural deficits, such as inadequate transportation networks and unreliable energy supplies, increase the cost of doing business and deter investment, even in a liberalized financial environment (Adeoye and Elegbede, 2012). Additionally, limited access to finance, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), constrains their ability to invest and expand, undermining the potential benefits of interest rate liberalization (Onakoya and Somoye, 2013).

Moreover, the regulatory environment plays a significant role in shaping investment outcomes. A stable and transparent regulatory framework is essential for building investor confidence and ensuring that financial market liberalization translates into tangible economic benefits. This includes strengthening financial institutions, improving governance, and ensuring the rule of law, which are critical for creating a favorable investment climate (Ibrahim & Sare, 2018).

Furthermore, addressing macroeconomic stability is vital for maximizing the impact of interest rate liberalization. High inflation and exchange rate volatility can erode investor confidence and reduce the attractiveness of investment opportunities. Policymakers should therefore, focus on implementing sound monetary policies that stabilize prices and, provide a conducive environment for investment. The study has highlighted the multifaceted nature of the relationship between interest rate liberalization and investment in Nigeria. While the findings underscore the potential of liberalization

efforts to enhance financial efficiency, they also point to the need for a coordinated policy approach that integrates monetary, fiscal, and structural reforms. This is crucial for maximizing the benefits of interest rate liberalization and fostering a conducive environment for investment and economic growth.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

This research investigates the influence of interest rate liberalization on investment in Nigeria, exploring the dynamic of various economic factors that shape investment. The study's findings are rooted in extensive econometric analysis, including unit root tests, F-bounds tests, and both long- and short-run models, complemented by Granger causality tests. The objective is to determine whether interest rate liberalization has substantially influenced investment in Nigeria within the period under review. Utilizing a robust econometric model, the research analyzed data spanning multiple decades to assess the relationships between gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) and key economic indicators, including exchange rate (EXR), public expenditure (PubExp), interest rate (INR.LEND), inflation rate (INF), and money supply (MS). The results revealed that interest rate liberalization has an impact on investment in Nigeria. The long-run analysis indicated that while interest rates and public expenditure significantly affect investment, the roles of exchange rate, inflation, and money supply are less pronounced. This complexity reflects Nigeria's unique economic space, characterized by its reliance on oil, fluctuating fiscal policies, and varying levels of economic stability. Short-run dynamics further illuminated these relationships, showing that public expenditure and interest rates have immediate and significant impacts on investment, with deviations from long-run equilibrium quickly corrected. This highlights the critical role of government spending and effective interest rate policies in shaping the investment climate.

Despite the potential of interest rate liberalization to enhance financial market efficiency, the study concludes that it cannot single-handedly drive investment growth. The absence of significant causality from interest rates to investment emphasizes the need for a comprehensive policy framework that incorporates fiscal measures and structural reforms. This is particularly relevant given Nigeria's infrastructural deficits, regulatory challenges, and limited access to finance, which constrain investment opportunities.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were proffered;

- i. Policymakers should prioritize stabilizing prices of goods and services, and exchange rates to foster a conducive environment for investment.
- ii. Given the finding that interest rate liberalization alone does not significantly drive investment, the government should focus on improving its financial infrastructure. This involves expanding access to credit for businesses, particularly small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs), which often face hurdles in obtaining financing. By strengthening credit facilities and reducing bureaucratic barriers, the government can create a more inclusive financial system that empowers businesses to invest and grow..
- iii. It is crucial for policymakers to develop fiscal policies that complement interest rate liberalization. This includes increasing public investment in infrastructure such as

transportation, energy, and telecommunications, which can reduce operational costs for businesses and enhance productivity.

iv. Fiscal incentives, such as tax rebate or subsidies for sectors with high growth potential, can attract both domestic and foreign investment, fostering a more vibrant economy and promoting investment.

v. The government should prioritize policies that are aimed at controlling inflation through effective monetary policy and fiscal discipline. There is need to establish a clear, transparent, and consistent economic policies that will build investor confidence, and reduce the perceived risk of investing in Nigeria.

vi. Policy framework and reforms to streamline regulatory processes, eliminate corruption, and enhance the efficiency of legal and institutional frameworks that will encourage investment in Nigeria should be put in place.

vii. Macroeconomic stability is vital for sustaining investor confidence. Volatile inflation and exchange rates can deter investment by increasing risk and uncertainty. Therefore, maintaining macroeconomic stability through sound monetary and fiscal policies as well as strategic investments in infrastructure, education, and regulatory reforms, for a more robust and diversified economy.

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